

To Determine the Effectiveness of Grapevine as a Communication Method in Tertiary Management

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Abstract

With the use of numerous social media sites, technology has enabled cheap and fast communication. Grapevine was traditionally passed from one person to another without the use of intermediaries. Due to social media, the rate of information sharing by grapevine has increased greatly. The aim of this study is to determine the efficacy of grapevine as a contact technique in tertiary administration during the COVID-19 pandemic. A case study was conducted in the Department of Computer Science at a Zimbabwean state university. Employees and students who received information from managers in a formal way were opposed to those who received information via the grapevine. Document processing and interviews were used to gather the data. This data was analysed, and the efficiency of grapevine was calculated. The efficiency of grapevine correspondence was assessed in terms of the information that could be obtained, the accuracy of the information, the degree of manipulation, the rate of transmission from sender to receiver, and whether two-way communication was possible.

Keywords: Administration, Grapevine, Listening, Information, Portal, Social Media

Introduction

According to the Australian Communications Consumer Action Network, social networking on social media networks entails using the internet to link consumers with their peers, relatives, and acquaintances (2019). While this does happen in some cases, social media networks are not all about finding new people online. Instead, they're mainly about connecting with people you already meet, such as peers, families, and acquaintances. Grapevine conversations, according to Patil (2017), are informal office dialogues in their purest form. Conversations between employees/subordinates and supervisors who do not obey any defined structure, protocol, or rule-based system are distinguished by it. At tertiary universities, there is usually a proper framework used in terms of coordination and the administration is set up on a hierarchical structure that often demarcates the administration structure in terms of decision making. The chairperson of the department reports to the Dean, who reports directly to the Vice Chancellor. This study looked at whether grapevine correspondence is a useful method in tertiary administration. A case study was conducted at a Zimbabwean state university. In section 2, the study included a brief perspective on communication, followed by a description of the methods in section 3, and finally, data presentation in section 4.

2. The History of Communication Types

The transmission of information from one person to another is known as communication (Newstrom & Davis 1993 as cited in Kapfunde, 2000). Grapevine, Downward, Upward, Lateral, and Internal-External contact are common forms of communication of communication. These can also be used for a Zimbabwean tertiary institution.

2.1 Correspondence via the grapevine

According to Patil, grapevine correspondence is an informal office conversation in its purest form (2017). Grapevine contact spreads quickly and is likely to reach any single individual in the company. The level and scope of grapevine contact are determined by the social and personal relationships of participants within an organization. It's an unavoidable consequence in office correspondence. Furthermore, Patil (2017) listed the following benefits of grapevine contact in tertiary institutions:

- It is a more efficient mode of communicating than traditional communication.
- It fosters interpersonal relationships within an organization
- Grapevine networking can be used successfully by senior executives to communicate good and optimistic thoughts or news, which can raise morale.

The following are some of the drawbacks of grapevine communication:

- There is a high risk of message distortion since the sender's messages can be corrupted before they reach the recipient.
- Since this method of correspondence typically lacks standardized networks, workers are free to express whatever they wish without risk of being identified or corrected. If the tweets are inflammatory, they may have a negative impact on the workplace.
- If workers are unsure about a grapevine post, they have no way of knowing if the details are right.
- Since most individuals want to keep their role in the dissemination of knowledge a secret, certain communications can be restricted to small communities.
- When harmful content is disseminated, identifying the individual or persons responsible for disseminating the message can be difficult.
- If employees are often the last to hear about important developments and facts that can be shared with all employees. The relationship between upper management and workers is deteriorating.
- If the government attempts to monitor grapevine messages, certain workers can find that upper management is concerned too much with how they can interact.

Downward Communication

Downward communication is communication that flows from the top to the bottom, such as from the Vice Chancellor to the students. It passes from senior management to lower-level employees (Kukreja,2017). Downward correspondence includes university aims, mottos, expectations, positive notes, work-related orders, newsletters, and letters from the VC or Dean's office.

2.3 Upward Listening

According to Kukreja, this contact refers to any communication that passes from workers to bosses, supervisors to administrators, and directors to executives (2017). Upward communication refers to communication between departments and faculties, as well as faculties and higher academic boards. Employee recommendations, success assessment notes, and reviews on proposed university plans are also examples of upward contact in the university sense.

2.4 Communication on the Hand

According to Papa (1997), lateral contact occurs in an entity and is neither upward nor downward. It moves horizontally and takes place between representatives that are on a rank of equals and peers. As a result, one crucial thing to remember in any lateral correspondence is that the receiver and sender's organizational stages or roles are usually very similar.

2.5 Communication with Internal and External Parties

Internal contact, according to Toppre (2019), occurs within the company or group—among people within and between various classes of employees. Oral or written communication, visual or audio-visual communication, and upward or downward communication are both possibilities. As a result, internal contact is used to notify, advise, teach, inspire, persuade, interest, steer, monitor, and caution employees. External communication, unlike internal communication, is directed outward. It speaks to people outside the business, such as prospective students, rivals, the general public, parents, the media, and the government.

2.6 Social Media Usage

Social media can be expressed in many ways that is why we have so many definitions over the internet. There is more of a kind of description what is the process of social media by underlying the interaction among people in which they are creating, sharing, exchanging, modifying their ideas in virtual communities or networks: “Social Media is a group of Internet based applications that build on the ideological foundations of Web 2.0, and that allow the creation and exchange of User Generated Content”.(Kaplan, A & Haenlein, M., 2010, p .61).

Traditionally, people used the Internet to expend content: they read it, watched it, and used it to buy goods, products and services. These days the internet is mainly being used for social networking using platforms such as whatsapp, Facebook and Instagram. Social media hence is influencing people’s ability to think independently. According to Hutton, G. & Fosdick, M. (2019) a study from Hewlett Packard Labs on social influence in online recommender systems measured how choices were changed by other people when facing different levels of confirmation and different conformity pressures. The results showed that some people’s opinions significantly sway people’s personal choices. Some people were more likely to adjust their own choices if some time had elapsed and when facing a number of opposing opinions. The results showed the great influence social media has on communication styles within the workplace. This notion served as the pivotal point of focus of the research.

3 Methodology

Many researchers have classified research methods into quantitative, qualitative and mixed methods (Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2013; Garrett, 2016). This research involved both quantitative and qualitative methods. Quantitative approach measured the effectiveness of communicating through grapevine in terms of the information being able to be accessed, clearness, and level of distortion and rate of transmission from sender to receiver.

A research strategy is how the researcher intends to carry out the work (Saunders, 2009). Research strategies include case studies, experiments, surveys, ethnography, grounded theory, action research and archival research. In this study, the researchers used a case study research strategy. A case study is a research strategy used to study phenomenon in a real-life context. The case used was that of department of Computer Science as the researchers are members of that department, hence aware of its flow of communication.

According to Creswell (2017), a target population is the whole group in which the researcher intends to select the sample for the purpose conducting a scientific inquiry or making observations about a phenomenon. In other words, a target population encompasses individuals, groups, organisations and objects who are eligible for selection as tine study sample. The research target population were employees and students of the Computer Science department. The department comprised of seven (7) members, five teaching staff and two technicians. Level two students (Fifty-seven students) within the department were also part of sample population chosen as it would be easier to be in touch with them during the lockdown period as the researchers were also teaching them in one or two modules.

A research instrument is a measurement dimension that is employed by researchers to gather appropriate data from the study participants (Zohrabi, 2015). The instruments used were interviews and document

analysis. Analysis of documents was done through the departmental Whatsapp group and Institute lectures' group. Interviews were mainly conducted via Whatsapp and Skype where possible. Physical face-to-face posed as a challenge due the COVID-19 pandemic.

The data collected included eight (8) randomly selected, different information which was retrieved through grapevine and eight (8) randomly selected different messages which were retrieved through formal communication. **Table 1** showed information which was circulated through grapevine and by formal means. The number of people interviewed per each information circulated is shown on the table. After collection of the data, it was analysed quantitatively and qualitatively.

Table 1: Messages Communicated By the University Administration

	Information disseminated Grapevine by means	Information disseminated by Formal means
1	Salary date	Salary date
2	Date of closure of the University due to COVID-19	Date of closure of the University due to COVID-19
3	Introduction of University Online virtual Classroom (MOVC)	Introduction of University Online virtual Classroom (MOVC)
4	Invitation for faculty seminar presentations.	Invitation for faculty seminar presentations.
5	Safety Guidelines in relation to COVID-19	Safety Guidelines in relation to COVID-19
6	Amount of school fees to be paid by students	Amount of school fees to be paid by students
7	Salary increment	Salary increment
8	Allocation of a certain module to be taught by a certain lecturer.	Allocation of a certain module to be taught by a certain lecturer.

4 Results Presentation & Discussion

This section presented data obtained during the research study. Data which related to accessing information through grapevine and formal means was obtained and analysed using software packages like Microsoft Word, Microsoft Excel and SPSS. Data was presented and analysed according to themes used in testing effectiveness of grapevine communication.

Theme 1: Access of information.

The goal of this theme was to check the ratio of people who obtained information through grapevine and also formal communication.

Table 2: Information disseminated by Grapevine

	Information disseminated by Grapevine means	No. of people interviewed	No. that accessed information	%
1	Salary date	7	6	86
2	Date of closure of the University due to COVID-19	57	48	84
3	Introduction of University Online virtual Classroom (MOVC)	57	10	18
4	Invitation for faculty seminar presentations.	7	3	43
5	Safety Guidelines in relation to COVID-19	57	15	26
6	Amount of school fees to be paid by students	7	6	86
7	Salary increment	7	5	71
8	Allocation of a certain module to be taught by a certain lecturer.	7	3	43
		Average		57

Table 2 showed the number of people (students and staff members who were interviewed to get responses on whether they received the information when it was disseminated via grapevine. The results showed that on average 57% managed to receive the information, for all the eight messages that were circulating through grapevine.

Table 3: Information disseminated through Formal means

	Information disseminated by Formal means	No. of people interviewed	No. that accessed information	percentage
1	Salary date	7	6	86
2	Date of closure of the University due to COVID-19	57	55	96
3	Introduction of University Online virtual Classroom (MOVC)	57	49	86
4	Invitation for faculty seminar presentations.	7	7	100
5	Safety Guidelines in relation to COVID-19	57	50	88
6	Amount of school fees to be paid by students	7	7	100
7	Salary increment	7	7	100
8	Allocation of a certain module to be taught by a certain lecturer.	7	7	100
			Average	94

Table 3 showed the percentage number of people who received the information when it was communicated using formal means. The results showed that on average 94% received the information. The formal means used were the university staff and student portal.

Figure 1: Percentage who accessed the Information.

As shown on Figure 1, in the department of computer science information did travel through grapevine however more employees and students obtained the information through formal means.

Theme 2: Clear information

The aim of this theme was to check the ratio of people who managed to receive the information in a clear way, for both grapevine and also formal communication.

Table 4: Clear Information- Grapevine Communication

	Information disseminated by Grapevine means	No. of people interviewed	No. of people :information is clear	%
1	Salary date	6	5	83
2	Date of closure of the University due to COVID-19	48	40	83
3	Introduction of University Online virtual Classroom (MOVC)	10	9	90
4	Invitation for faculty seminar presentations.	3	2	67
5	Safety Guidelines in relation to COVID-19	15	10	67
6	Amount of school fees to be paid by students	6	3	50
7	Salary increment	5	2	40
8	Allocation of a certain module to be taught by a certain lecturer.	3	1	33
			Average	64

Table 4 represented the number of staff members and students who found the information to be very clear when they received it through grapevine means. There was a deduction in terms of the number of people interviewed as some out the total sample population could not access the information via the internet or social networks. On average it showed that 64% found the information to be very clear.

Table 5: Clear Information- Formal Communication

	Information disseminated by Formal means	No. of people interviewed	No. of people :information is clear	%
1	Salary date	6	6	100
2	Date of closure of the University due to COVID-19	55	55	100
3	Introduction of University Online virtual Classroom (MOVC)	49	48	98
4	Invitation for faculty seminar presentations.	7	7	100
5	Safety Guidelines in relation to COVID-19	50	48	96
6	Amount of school fees to be paid by students	7	7	100
7	Salary increment	7	6	86
8	Allocation of a certain module to be taught by a certain lecturer.	7	7	100
		Average		97

Table 5 represented the number of staff members and students who found the information to be very clear when they received it through formal means. There was a deduction in terms of the number of people interviewed as some out the total sample population could not access the information via the internet or social networks. On average it showed that 97% found the information to be very clear.

Figure 2: % of Clear Information

97% of the people who accessed information through formal way said the message was clear. A low number of 64% said the information they got through grapevine was clear.

Theme 3: Distorted information

The aim of this theme was to check the ratio of people who received distorted information in any way, for both grapevine and also formal communication.

Table 6: Distorted Information through Grapevine

	Information disseminated by Grapevine means	No. of people interviewed	No. of people :information is distorted	%
1	Salary date	6	6	100
2	Date of closure of the University due to COVID-19	48	5	10
3	Introduction of University Online virtual Classroom (MOVC)	10	0	0
4	Invitation for faculty seminar presentations.	3	3	100
5	Safety Guidelines in relation to COVID-19	15	0	0

6	Amount of school fees to be paid by students	6	5	83
7	Salary increment	5	0	0
8	Allocation of a certain module to be taught by a certain lecturer.	3	2	67
Average				45

Table

6

represented the number of staff members and students who found the information to be distorted when they received it through grapevine means. There was a deduction in terms of the number of people interviewed as some out the total sample population could not access the information via the internet or social networks. This means when the information was then confirmed it was found to be different with what they received. On average it showed that 45% found the information to be distorted.

Table 7: Distorted Information – Formal Means

	Information disseminated by Formal means	No. of people interviewed	No. of people :information is distorted	%
1	Salary date	6	1	17
2	Date of closure of the University due to COVID-19	55	0	0
3	Introduction of University Online virtual Classroom (MOVC)	49	0	0
4	Invitation for faculty seminar presentations.	7	0	0
5	Safety Guidelines in relation to COVID-19	50	0	0
6	Amount of school fees to be paid by students	7	0	0
7	Salary increment	7	0	0
8	Allocation of a certain module to be taught by a certain lecturer.	7	0	0
Average				2

Table 7 showed that 2% of the students and staff received distorted information when formal communication was used.

Figure 3: Distorted Information

Figure 3 showed that information circulated through formal ways is more accurate than that circulated through grapevine. Only 2% said the information was distorted. From the interview done the grapevine information was distorted because the messages they got were not complete or different versions were said about the same thing.

Theme 4: Degree of travel of information

The goal of this theme was to measure the degree of travel of the information for both methods of communication. The rate determined was whether it was slow or faster depending on the questions posed to the respondents.

Table 8: Degree of travel

	No. of people interviewed	No. that received grapevine first	%
Salary date	6	6	100
Date of closure of the University due to COVID-19	48	40	83

Introduction of University Online virtual Classroom (MOVC)	10	4	40
Invitation for faculty seminar presentations.	3	2	67
Safety Guidelines in relation to COVID-19	15	15	100
Amount of school fees to be paid by students	6	5	83
Salary increment	5	5	100
Allocation of a certain module to be taught by a certain lecturer.	3	2	67
Average			80

As shown in **Table 8** there was a deduction in terms of the number of people interviewed as some out the total sample population could not access the information via the internet or social networks. Grapevine information travelled faster than formal information. 80% of the people receive information through grapevine. This meant that 20% missed the grapevine messages and only received strictly formal messages. Then they got the same information later through formal communication.

Theme 5: Two way communication

This was created to check whether grapevine and formal communication facilitated two way communication as this ensures effective communication.

Table 9: Two way communication- Grapevine

	Information disseminated by Grapevine means	No. of people interviewed	No. that supported allowance of two way communication	%
1	Salary date	6	1	17
2	Date of closure of the University due to COVID-19	48	2	4
3	Introduction of University Online virtual Classroom (MOVC)	10	3	30
4	Invitation for faculty seminar presentations.	3	0	0
5	Safety Guidelines in relation to COVID-19	15	0	0
6	Amount of school fees to be paid by students	6	0	0
7	Salary increment	5	1	20
8	Allocation of a certain module to be taught by a certain lecturer.	3	1	33
Average				13

From **Table 9** showed above on average 13% supported the notion that a two way communication is possible using grapevine with source of information known while most had no idea of the origin of the messages.

Table 10: Two way communication - Formal

	Information disseminated by Formal means	No. of people interviewed	No. that supported allowance of two way communication	%
1	Salary date	6	3	50
2	Date of closure of the University due to COVID-19	55	49	89
3	Introduction of University Online virtual Classroom (MOVC)	49	25	51
4	Invitation for faculty seminar presentations.	7	6	86
5	Safety Guidelines in relation to COVID-19	50	35	70
6	Amount of school fees to be paid by students	7	5	71
7	Salary increment	7	5	71
8	Allocation of a certain module to be taught by a certain lecturer.	7	7	100
Average				74

From **Table 10** it was shown that on average 74% of the people interviewed said that there was a two way communication with the source of information. Some could even respond via email to the messages they

received using formal channels. There was a deduction in terms of the number of people interviewed as some out the total sample population could not access the information via the internet or social networks.

Figure 4: Two Way Communication

Figure 4 showed that grapevine lacks the 2 way communication. Received information cannot be given feedback to the source. Only 13% of the people were able to do the 2 way communication under grapevine information.

Table 11: Summary of Results

	Average % who accessed the information	Average % that said information was clear	Average % who said information was distorted	Average % that said they received grapevine first	Average % that supported allowance of two way communication
Grapevine communication	57	64	45	80	13
Formal communication	94	97	2	-----	74

Table 11 summarises the average statistics obtained according to analysed five themes.

Grapevine was proved to be not an effective way of communication in tertiary administration. From the study above, formal communication was more accessible than grapevine communication. 94% of people accessed the formal communication as compared to 57% of people who accessed grapevine. Formal communication was clearer than grapevine communication. Grapevine information was more distorted than formal information. In grapevine communication it was difficult to have a two way communication since the source of information cannot be easily identified. However grapevine information travelled faster than formal communication.

5 Conclusion and recommendations

In summary grapevine communication in tertiary administration was found to be not effective. Therefore Tertiary institutions must not rely on employees getting information through grapevine. At least one of the formal ways should be employed to relay information between superiors and employees and students. In

cases where grapevine may not be eliminated, it may only be used as a supplement to formal communication. The administration personal should minimise grapevine by:

- Establishing to employees and students a zero tolerance to grapevine which is harmful, inflammatory or image tarnishing.
- Explaining how the organisation communicates.
- Quickly dismissing an untruthful rumour which might be spreading in the organisation. The more you delay in dismissing the more the people believe the grapevine.
- Creating various ways of communication like newsletters, email, open door policy etc.
- Whenever something has arisen and employees and students need to know. The administration should not delay in disseminating information. Keeping them in suspense causes others to spread rumours.

To match the fast rate at which grapevine information travels, management should investigate the media responsible for transmitting grapevine in a faster way. This media will then be in cooperated among other formal ways communication. Under this study it was deduced that employees and students receive formal communication mainly through staff and student portal. However they don't check the portal regularly. They receive grapevine information through Whatsapp media as they check their Whatsapp almost on instant bases once they receive a message. Thus grapevine communication travelled faster than formal communication. Therefore Whatsapp should be added as a secondary media to circulate information.

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